

1 **Short Title:** *Arabidopsis thaliana* plastid carbonic anhydrases

2 **Title:** *Arabidopsis* plastid carbonic anhydrases are required for growth on ambient air

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9 **One sentence summary:** In this study, we show that *Arabidopsis* plastid carbonic
10 anhydrase activity is required for growth on ambient air.

11 **List of author contributions:**

12 HNW, RJD, VCR, DJL and JVM - designed the research; HNW, RJD, VCR, AKR, LML
13 and VDF - performed the research; HNW, DJL and JVM - Analyzed the data; and HNW
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21 **Running head:** Plastid carbonic anhydrases of *Arabidopsis thaliana*

22

23

24 **Abstract**

25 Carbonic anhydrases (CAs) are zinc-metalloenzymes that catalyze the interconversion of
26 CO₂ and HCO₃⁻. In heterotrophic organisms, CAs are known to provide HCO₃⁻ for
27 metabolic pathways that require a carboxylation step. Arabidopsis has 14 α- and β-type
28 CAs. In this study, we show that Arabidopsis has two plastid CAs designated as βCA1
29 and βCA5. To study their physiological properties, we obtained knock-out (KO) lines for
30 βCA1 (SALK_106570) and βCA5 (SALK_121932). These mutant lines were confirmed
31 by genomic PCR, RT-PCR and Western blots. While the *βca1* KO plants grew normally
32 in our test growth studies, the growth of the *βca5* KO plants was stunted when grown
33 under ambient CO₂ conditions, 400 μL L⁻¹. High CO₂ conditions, 30,000 μL L⁻¹, partially
34 rescued their growth. These results were surprising, as βCA1 is more abundant than
35 βCA5 in leaves. However, a study of the tissue expression patterns for these genes
36 indicated that *βCA1* is expressed only in shoot tissue, while *βCA5* is expressed
37 throughout the plant. We hypothesize that βCA5 compensates for the loss of βCA1, but
38 due to its expression being limited to only leaves, βCA1 cannot compensate for the loss
39 of βCA5. We also present data demonstrating that βCA5 is supplying HCO₃⁻ required for
40 anaplerotic pathways that take place in plastids, such as fatty acid synthesis.

41

42 Introduction

43 Carbonic anhydrases (CAs) are ubiquitous in nature, catalyzing the
44 interconversion of CO₂ and HCO₃⁻. While most CAs are zinc metalloenzymes, there are
45 multiple structurally and sequentially distinct families found across many different species.
46 In fact, at least eight different CA families (alpha – iota) have been described, with some
47 of the CAs having structural as well as catalytic functions (Hewett-Emmett and Tashian,
48 1996; DiMario et al., 2017; Jensen et al., 2020). CAs aid a variety of different biological
49 functions. For example, in mammals, where the internal CO₂ concentration is very high
50 (30,000 μL L⁻¹ in air), the CO₂ to HCO₃⁻ interconversion acts as a major buffer in the blood.
51 However, plants and many microorganisms operate at ambient levels of CO₂ (400 μL L⁻¹
52 in air). In these organisms, a major function of CAs is to supply CO₂ or HCO₃⁻ for various
53 metabolic pathways. Photosynthesis is the best example of a pathway requiring CO₂,
54 while reactions in nucleic acid, amino acid and fatty acid biosynthesis all require HCO₃⁻.
55 Without CAs, these pathways can be starved for carbon. For example, *Escherichia coli*
56 has two CAs, while *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* has one CA isoform. Knocking out all the
57 CAs in either *E. coli* or *S. cerevisiae* results in strains that can no longer grow on ambient
58 levels of CO₂. These CA knock-out (KO) lines can still grow on elevated CO₂ levels.
59 Supplementing the *S. cerevisiae* KO lines with nucleic acids and fatty acids restores
60 growth at ambient levels of CO₂ (Aguilera et al., 2005). The synthesis of fatty acids,
61 purines and pyrimidines all require a carboxylation step. Adding the nucleic or fatty acids
62 allow the yeast to bypass the carboxylation step needed. Hoang and Chapman (2002)
63 also showed that inhibiting CA inhibited lipid biosynthesis in cotton embryos. In the case
64 of lipid biosynthesis, the carboxylation catalyzed by ACCase is the affected step because
65 the enzyme has low affinity for HCO₃. The working hypothesis is that CA activity is needed
66 to supply HCO₃⁻ for fatty acid biosynthesis since the $K_m(\text{HCO}_3^-)$ is in the range of 1-2 mM
67 (DiMario et al., 2017). At ambient levels of CO₂ and pH 7, the HCO₃⁻ concentration would
68 only be 100-200 μM, or well below the $K_m(\text{HCO}_3^-)$. In the absence of CA, the HCO₃⁻
69 concentration would be reduced even below that level.

70 Flowering plants possess members of the αCA, βCA, and γCA families (Hewett-
71 Emmett and Tashian, 1996). αCAs are generally monomers with the zinc atom

72 coordinated by three histidine residues and one water molecule organized in a tetrahedral
73 conformation (Liljas et al., 1972). The active unit of the β CA is a dimer where the active
74 site is located at the interface of the two monomers (Kimber and Pai, 2000). In β CAs, the
75 zinc is coordinated by coordinated by two cysteine residues, one histidine residue, and a
76 water molecule. In contrast, γ CAs are trimers that have their active site zinc ion situated
77 at the interface of two subunits coordinated by histidine residues from both subunits
78 (Kisker et al., 1996; Iverson et al., 2000).

79 The *Arabidopsis* (*Arabidopsis thaliana*) genome has eight α CA genes, six β CA
80 genes and five genes that encode three γ CA proteins and two γ -like proteins. The γ CA
81 genes are highly expressed, with the γ CA proteins and γ -like proteins interacting to form
82 an extra structure on complex I of the mitochondrial electron transport chain (DiMario et
83 al., 2016). In most plant tissues, the α CAs are poorly expressed or are not expressed at
84 all. Only α CA1, α CA2, and α CA3 are expressed in leaf tissue. In contrast, the β CA genes
85 are highly expressed, with the β CA proteins making up as much as 1% of the soluble
86 protein in leaves (Tobin, 1970). The six β CA isoforms are found in several subcellular
87 locations. β CA1 and β CA5 have been localized to the chloroplast (Fabre et al., 2007; Hu
88 et al., 2010), while β CA2, β CA3, β CA4.2 are found in the cytosol (Fabre et al., 2007;
89 DiMario et al., 2016). The other two β CAs, β CA4.1 and β CA6, have been reported to be
90 localized in the plasma membrane (DiMario et al., 2016) and the mitochondria (Fabre et
91 al., 2007) respectively. However, even though the β CA genes are highly expressed,
92 single KO lines for most of the β CA genes do not display significant growth phenotypes
93 (Medina-Puche et al., 2017). This might be because more than one CA is present in a
94 compartment within the plant cell. For example, β CA2, β CA3 and β CA4.2 are all present
95 in the cytoplasm and reduced growth is only seen if more than one of the proteins are
96 disrupted (DiMario et al., 2016). While most single KO lines do not show a strong growth
97 phenotype, knocking out only the β CA5 gene in *Arabidopsis* results in stunted, sterile
98 plants when grown on ambient CO₂ (Medina-Puche et al., 2017). The purpose of this
99 communication is to report why β CA5 is so important for normal plant growth.

100

101

102 **Results**

103 **Subcellular location of β CA1 and β CA5**

104 Both β CA1 and β CA5 are predicted to be chloroplast proteins and proteomics data
105 indicate that both β CA1 and β CA5 are found in the chloroplast (Sun et al., 2009). Studies
106 using GFP fusions have also shown that β CA1 and β CA5 are localized to the chloroplast
107 (Fabre et al., 2007) Transient expression assays, however, also indicated that β CA1
108 might be present on the plasma membrane (Hu et al., 2010). To confirm that β CA1 and
109 β CA5 are both chloroplast proteins, the eGFP coding region was fused to the 3' end of
110 the β CA1 and β CA5 genomic regions and transformed into Arabidopsis. Protoplasts
111 generated from stably transformed Arabidopsis plants expressing either $35S::\beta$ CA1-
112 *eGFP* or $35S::\beta$ CA5-*eGFP* clearly showed that β CA1 and β CA5 are found in the
113 chloroplast, as the CA-eGFP signals co-localized with the chlorophyll autofluorescence
114 (Fig. 1 and Fig. S1).

115

116 **Plants with T-DNA insertions in β ca1 or β ca5 no longer express that CA**

117 Alleles containing T-DNA disruptions to each gene, SALK_106570 for the β ca1 line and
118 SALK_121932 for the β ca5 line, were obtained from TAIR to determine the effect of β CA1
119 and β CA5 on plant growth. The SALK_106570 insert is located within the ninth exon of
120 the β CA1 gene, and the SALK_121932 insert is located in the eighth exon of the β CA5
121 gene (Fig. 2A). Genomic PCR using β CA1 or β CA5 gene-specific primers was used to
122 confirm the specific T-DNA gene disruptions. In addition, a primer specific to the T-DNA
123 insert was paired with a gene-specific primer to confirm the location of each T-DNA in its
124 respective gene (Fig. S2A). To confirm that these mutants are T-DNA KO lines, reverse
125 transcription-PCR was performed (Fig. S2B). The results indicated that β CA1 and β CA5
126 transcripts were present in the wild-type but absent in their respective mutant lines.
127 Western blots were also performed using antibodies directed against either Arabidopsis
128 β CA1 and β CA5 (Fig. 2B). The β CA1 and β CA5 protein bands were detected at 25.7 and
129 26.8 kDa, respectively. Figure 2B shows that the β CA1 and β CA5 proteins were missing
130 in their respective mutant lines.

131 **Growth of the *βca5* and *βca1βca5* lines is severely reduced at ambient CO₂, but not**
132 **high CO₂**

133 Plants missing βCA1 (*βca1*), βCA5 (*βca5*) or both CAs (*βca1βca5*) were compared to the
134 wild-type (COL) when grown at ambient and elevated levels of CO₂. The *βca5* and
135 *βca1βca5* plants grown for 6 weeks at 400 μL L⁻¹ CO₂ and an 8-h day length were smaller
136 than both wild-type and *βca1* plants (Fig. 3A). However, the growth of *βca5* and *βca1βca5*
137 plants were similar to wild-type and *βca1* plants when grown at 30,000 μL L⁻¹ CO₂ (Fig.
138 3A). The weekly average above ground fresh weights of the wild-type and *βca1* were
139 comparable under all growth conditions, indicating that loss of βCA1 by itself did not affect
140 plant growth (Fig. 3C). In contrast, the growth of *βca5* and *βca1βca5* plants was
141 significantly reduced when grown at 400 μL L⁻¹ CO₂ (Fig. 3). The poor growth exhibited
142 by the *βca5* KO plants was unexpected, as βCA1 is far more abundant in leaf tissue than
143 βCA5. The apparent normal growth of the *βca1* KO plants was also notable since βCA1
144 is so abundant in leaves.

145

146 **Tissue expression patterns of βCA1 and βCA5**

147 RNA-seq data indicates βCA1 is expressed in shoot tissue while βCA5 is expressed
148 throughout the plant (Fig. 4A). RNA-seq studies from a number of research groups show
149 the expression of βCA1 is undetectable in root tissue (Fig. 4A; Zhang et al., 2020). βCA1
150 shows leaf-specific expression similar to the expression pattern of photosystem II
151 manganese stabilizing polypeptide (*PsbO*). In contrast, βCA5 is expressed in all tissues
152 examined, similar to γCA1 expression (Fig. 4A). The expression pattern observed in RNA-
153 seq data was confirmed using GUS expression driven by the βCA1 and βCA5 promoters
154 (Fig. 4B and Fig. 4C). In these assays, GUS expression was very high in leaf tissue when
155 driven by the βCA1 promoter (Fig. 4B). However, GUS expression was undetectable in
156 root tissue when driven by the βCA1 promoter (Fig. 4C). In contrast, GUS expression was
157 seen in both the roots and shoots when the βCA5 promoter was used (Fig. 4B and Fig.
158 4C). This expression pattern was further confirmed using antibodies raised against either
159 βCA1 or βCA5 (Fig. S3A and Fig. S3B). In these studies, no βCA1 protein was detected

160 in root tissue, but β CA5 was clearly detected in both roots and shoots (Fig. S3A and Fig.
161 S3B).

162

163 **β CA1 or β CA5 can complement the β ca5 plants**

164 The hypothesis that the poor growth exhibited by the β ca5 KO plants was due to the loss
165 of CA activity was validated in two ways. First, near-normal growth was restored when
166 the β ca5 plants were grown on elevated CO₂ (Fig. 3A). However, the amount of CO₂
167 required to restore near-normal growth was quite high (30,000 μ L L⁻¹). A second
168 confirmation that the reduced growth phenotype of the β ca5 mutant was due to the lack
169 of the plastid carbonic anhydrases arises from the observation that normal growth was
170 recovered once a plastid CA was reintroduced into the β ca5 plants. Constructs containing
171 the endogenous β CA5 promoter or ubiquitin promoter driving expression of either the
172 β CA1 or β CA5 coding sequence were assembled and transformed into the β ca5 line. The
173 genotyping of the complemented plant lines is shown in Figure S4B and Figure S4C.
174 When β CA5 driven by either a constitutive ubiquitin promoter or the endogenous β CA5
175 promoter was reintroduced into β ca5 plants, normal growth on ambient CO₂ was restored
176 (Fig. 5). Normal growth was also restored when the β CA1 gene driven by either the
177 constitutive ubiquitin promoter or the endogenous β CA5 promoter was inserted into the
178 β ca5 plants (Fig. 5). These results indicate that either plastid CA can complement the
179 loss of β CA5, considering that both β CA1 and β CA5 worked when using either the *UBI1*
180 or β CA5 promoters.

181

182 **Plastid CA activity is needed for fatty acid biosynthesis**

183 Growth and expression studies indicated that a loss of plastid CA activity in root tissue
184 might be the primary reason for the poor growth of the β ca5 plants at ambient CO₂. This
185 observation is similar to published data with *S. cerevisiae*, where knocking out CA activity
186 resulted in a mutant line unable to grow in ambient CO₂ (Götz et al., 1999). In *S.*
187 *cerevisiae*, Aguilera et al. (2005) identified four carboxylation reactions that required high
188 concentrations of HCO₃⁻. One pathway that requires a carboxylation step is fatty acid

189 biosynthesis, specifically ACCase which has a high $K_m(\text{HCO}_3^-)$ of 1-2 mM. ACCase
190 catalyzes the reaction shown in Equation 1 and is known to be located in plastids (Sasaki
191 and Nagano, 2004).

193 In plastids, the first step of fatty acid synthesis requires ACCase to add HCO_3^- to acetyl-
194 CoA to form malonyl-CoA. We hypothesized that lack of CA activity in root plastids limits
195 the carbon availability for ACCase, thus limiting fatty acid synthesis and reducing growth
196 in the $\beta ca5$ plants. We therefore attempted to restore normal growth to $\beta ca5$ plants by
197 bypassing the ACCase reaction by adding malonate to seedlings growing on agar plates.
198 As can be seen in Figure 6A, malonate significantly stimulated root growth in the $\beta ca5$
199 plants.

200

201 **$\beta CA5$ is required for male fertility in Arabidopsis**

202 We observed that male $\beta ca5$ plants are sterile when grown in ambient CO_2 . Like roots,
203 $\beta CA1$ is not expressed in pollen; however, $\beta CA5$ is expressed in pollen (Fig. 7). No pollen
204 germination was observed in $\beta ca5$ mutants when incubated overnight under ambient CO_2
205 (Fig. 8A). However, when pollen from $\beta ca5$ mutants was incubated overnight in high CO_2 ,
206 an average of 60% of pollen grains germinated (observed over three image frames) with
207 an average germ tube length around 50 μm (Fig. 8A). For the wild type, an average of
208 40% of pollen grains germinated (observed over three image frames) under ambient
209 conditions, with germ tube length around 20 μm (Fig. 8B). In high CO_2 , wild-type pollen
210 germination had increased to 80% with an average germ tube length around 80 μm (Fig.
211 8B). The $\beta ca5$ pollen's failure to germinate in ambient air supports the hypothesis that a
212 lack of plastid CA is the cause of the male sterility phenotype.

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218 Discussion

219 In this paper we present evidence that the Arabidopsis β CA1 and β CA5 proteins
220 are predominantly located in plastids. Also, by demonstrating their different expression
221 patterns, we show that these plastid CAs have different physiological functions in the
222 plant. Our data, as well as data from several RNA-seq studies, show the expression of
223 β CA1 to be undetectable in root tissue, while β CA5 is expressed in all tissues (Fig. 4).
224 GUS expression driven by the β CA1 and β CA5 promoters was examined to confirm the
225 expression pattern found in RNA-seq data (Fig. 4B and Fig. 4C). When driven by the
226 β CA1 promoter, GUS expression was very high in leaf tissue but undetectable in root
227 tissue. In contrast, GUS expression was seen in both the root and shoot when driven by
228 the β CA5 promoter. This expression pattern was further confirmed using antibodies
229 against β CA1 or β CA5 (Fig. S3). No β CA1 protein was detected in the root tissue during
230 these studies, but β CA5 was clearly detected in both roots and shoots (Fig. S3).

231 The most striking result of this paper was the poor growth of the β ca5 KO plants
232 when grown at ambient CO₂ (Fig. 3). We hypothesized that the poor growth exhibited by
233 the β ca5 KO plants was due to the loss of CA activity, which was supported by two
234 findings. First, near-normal growth was restored when the β ca5 plants were grown in
235 elevated CO₂ (Fig. 3A). However, a very high level of CO₂ (30,000 μ L L⁻¹) was required
236 to restore growth. Secondly, normal growth was recovered once a plastid CA was
237 reintroduced into the β ca5 plants. When β CA5 was put back into β ca5 plants driven by a
238 constitutive ubiquitin promoter or the β CA5 promoter, normal growth was restored on
239 ambient CO₂ (Fig. 5). Normal growth was also restored when β CA1 was put back into the
240 plant driven by a constitutive promoter (Fig. 5). From these results, it can be inferred that
241 any plastid CA can complement the loss of β CA5 because there was no observational
242 difference in growth phenotype between plants complimented with β CA5 vs β CA1. Either
243 gene worked as long as a constitutive promoter was utilized (*UB1* or β CA5). This
244 complementation approach is summarized in Figure 9.

245 A second surprising result was that the β ca1 mutant plants grew like wild-type
246 plants in ambient air. This is notable because β CA1 comprises nearly 1% of all soluble
247 protein in the leaf (Tobin, 1970). Also, β CA1 is expressed at much higher rates than β CA5
248 in leaves (Fig. 4A; Ferreira et al., 2008). Despite such high levels of β CA1 in the leaf, it

249 was the $\beta ca5$ mutant that showed a drastic growth reduction in ambient air. We
250 hypothesize that it is the differences in tissue expression of $\beta CA1$ and $\beta CA5$ that explain
251 these results. The lack of expression of $\beta CA1$ in roots suggests that root plastids have no
252 CA activity when we eliminate $\beta CA5$ expression using gene disruption (Fig. 4). This would
253 then cause defects in important anaplerotic pathways requiring a carboxylase step that
254 take place within plastids, like fatty acid biosynthesis. The lack of a plastid CA in the roots,
255 therefore, leads to the very poor growth phenotype of $\beta ca5$ plants on ambient CO_2 .

256 The $\beta ca5$ growth defect is reminiscent of the poor growth seen in *E. coli* and *S.*
257 *cerevisiae* CA KO lines when grown on air. *E. coli* and *S. cerevisiae* cells lacking CA
258 activity also cannot grow on ambient levels of CO_2 . Only very high levels of CO_2 ($>20,000$
259 $\mu L L^{-1}$) can restore normal growth in these mutants. Aguilera et al. (2005) hypothesized
260 that several biotin-dependent carboxylases involved in both nucleic acid and fatty acid
261 biosynthesis became starved for HCO_3^- when CA was deleted in *S. cerevisiae*. All of these
262 carboxylases have a $K_m(HCO_3^-)$ in the range of 1-2 mM, well above the 200 $\mu M HCO_3^-$
263 concentration in an aqueous solution in equilibrium with air at pH 7.0. They argued that
264 the CA in the cell replenished the HCO_3^- pools and the absence of CA would drive the
265 HCO_3^- down even further than the baseline 200 $\mu M HCO_3^-$ concentration. In support of
266 this idea, Aguilera et al. (2005) were able to restore normal growth of the CA-deficient *S.*
267 *cerevisiae* cells on air by adding nucleic acids and fatty acids to the growth medium. This
268 experiment strongly supports the idea that the *E. coli* CA KO lines were starved for HCO_3^-
269 in the absence of CA and were unable to make fatty acids.

270 In plants, two major metabolic pathways take place in plastids: fatty acid and lipid
271 biosynthesis (Ohlrogge and Browse, 1995). The plant carboxylases required for these
272 pathways also have high $K_m(HCO_3^-)$ (DiMario et al., 2017). ACCase is the enzyme that
273 catalyzes the first committed step of fatty acid biosynthesis, the addition of HCO_3^- to
274 acetyl-CoA to make malonyl-CoA. In plants, the $K_m(HCO_3^-)$ of ACCase is near 1.4 mM
275 (Herbert et al., 1996). With the assumptions that the leaf chloroplast stroma CO_2
276 concentration is 12 μM , the pH is 8.2, and equilibrium conditions are met, the stromal
277 HCO_3^- concentration would be near 750 μM . This concentration of HCO_3^- is well below
278 the $K_m(HCO_3^-)$ of ACCase. Therefore, the presence of a CA near ACCase may assist with
279 ACCase activity by maintaining the plastid HCO_3^- concentration. The disparity between

280 plastid HCO_3^- concentration and the ACCase $K_m(\text{HCO}_3^-)$ is likely to be even greater in the
281 roots. Since roots are not exposed to light, the plastids in root cells do not perform
282 photosynthesis and the pH of the plastid stroma is expected to be closer to neutral.
283 Assuming the root plastid stroma is at equilibrium, the HCO_3^- concentration will be much
284 lower than it is in leaf chloroplasts and the lack of a carbonic anhydrase interacting with
285 ACCase will be even more problematic. Indeed, the root systems of $\beta ca5$ plants are much
286 smaller than the root systems of wild-type plants (Fig. 6), which is consistent with this
287 proposed role for $\beta CA5$.

288 Hoang and Chapman (2002) provided evidence that CA is needed for lipid
289 biosynthesis in both cotton embryos and tobacco cell suspension. In their work, they
290 inhibited CA using a variety of sulfonamides, with ethoxzolamide being the most
291 effective. They also identified cDNAs encoding plastid-targeting CAs from the non-
292 photosynthetic cotyledon library. They found that lipid biosynthesis was severely inhibited
293 in cotton embryos and tobacco cell suspensions treated with the membrane-permeant
294 sulfonamide ethoxzolamide. Thus, lipid biosynthesis is correlated with HCO_3^- availability
295 in bacteria, fungi, animals (Lynch et al., 1995) and plants.

296 Growing $\beta ca5$ plants with supplemented malonate, which bypasses the ACCase
297 step of lipid synthesis, improved root growth of these mutant lines (Fig. 6). It is speculated
298 that malonate can be converted to malonyl-CoA by a homolog of malonyl-CoA synthetase
299 found in Arabidopsis (Baud et al., 2004). This possible bypass of the ACCase step was
300 demonstrated by Baud et al. (2004) where they found that malonate added exogenously
301 can partially compensate for the loss of cytosolic ACCase in Arabidopsis. We too were
302 able to partially compensate for the loss of plastid CA by adding malonate to germinating
303 mutant plants.

304 While doing crosses, we noticed that male $\beta ca5$ plants were sterile, which agrees
305 with the findings in Medina-Puche et al. (2017). When pollen germination was examined,
306 we found that $\beta ca5$ mutants were unable to put up pollen tubes under ambient CO_2 , but
307 demonstrated enhanced pollen germination and tube growth on elevated CO_2 . In fact, the
308 plants could be selfed if kept on very high CO_2 ($30,000 \mu\text{L L}^{-1}$ in air) for their entire life
309 cycle. Thus, our work suggests the functional importance of plastid CAs $\beta CA1$ and $\beta CA5$,
310 especially in fatty acid biosynthesis and pollen fertility.

311 The growth patterns of the Arabidopsis CA KO lines reported here differ from the
312 observations reported by Hines et al. (2021) using tobacco. In their work, plants missing
313 only $\beta CA1$ or only $\beta CA5$ grew normally. However, if both CA genes were disrupted, the
314 tobacco plants grew very poorly, similar to our observations with Arabidopsis. Hines et al.
315 (2021) hypothesized that lipid production was disrupted in the double mutant after finding
316 differences in lipid patterns. The differences between their results and our data are likely
317 due to differences between tobacco and Arabidopsis in the tissue expression patterns of
318 the two CAs. While Hines et al. (2021) did not report on the expression patterns of $\beta CA1$
319 or $\beta CA5$, it is reasonable to assume that both $\beta CA1$ and $\beta CA5$ are made in most or all
320 tissues in tobacco since either single mutant still grew normally. The fact that tobacco is
321 tetraploid makes it even more likely that both of the CAs are expressed in all tissues and
322 that the activities of $\beta CA1$ and $\beta CA5$ are redundant in tobacco. In Arabidopsis, the poor
323 growth on ambient CO₂ is observed in the $\beta ca5$ plants because $\beta CA1$ is not made in all
324 tissues. Our results are also consistent with earlier RNA antisense studies where
325 researchers lowered the expression of the chloroplastic $\beta CA1$ (Majeau et al., 1994; Price
326 et al., 2004; Ferreira et al., 2008). These earlier studies reported normal growth and
327 carbon assimilation rates in plants with reduced $\beta CA1$. If these earlier studies had
328 targeted $\beta CA5$ as well as $\beta CA1$, they likely would have found that the double knock-down
329 plants had poor growth on ambient CO₂. These earlier studies are consistent with the
330 hypothesis that $\beta CA5$ can compensate for the loss of $\beta CA1$ and that only a relatively low
331 amount of CA activity is required to support plant development.

332 A major take-away from our results is that $\beta CA1$ and $\beta CA5$ proteins have markedly
333 different functions within the plant. This idea is supported by the different tissue
334 expression patterns of $\beta CA1$ and $\beta CA5$, as seen with both RNA-seq data and the GUS
335 experiment (Fig. 4). The developmental defects that occur when $\beta CA5$ is knocked out
336 suggest that this enzyme is linked to anaplerotic pathways, supporting the Hoang and
337 Chapman (2002) hypothesis that CA is needed for lipid biosynthesis. If lipid synthesis is
338 reduced, cell division would be significantly impaired since there may not be sufficient
339 lipids for the plasma membranes of dividing cells. This could significantly limit the
340 development of some plant tissues, such as roots and pollen tubes.

341

342 **Materials and Methods**

343 **Plant lines and growth conditions**

344 All Arabidopsis wild-type and T-DNA plants used in this work are of the Columbia (COL)
345 ecotype. These plants were grown under ambient ($400 \mu\text{L L}^{-1} \text{CO}_2$) and 3% ($30,000 \mu\text{L}$
346 L^{-1}) CO_2 in 24-hour light at an intensity of $100 \mu\text{mol photons m}^{-2} \text{sec}^{-1}$. All plants used in
347 growth studies were watered every other day, alternating between distilled H_2O and a 1:3
348 dilution of Hoagland's nutrient solution in distilled H_2O (Epstein and Bloom, 2005). Plants
349 were grown in 3.5×3 in. pots. Sun grow professional growing mixture (METRO MIX 830)
350 was used as the potting media. For growth studies, plants were grown on either ambient
351 or $30,000 \mu\text{L L}^{-1}$ with $100 \mu\text{mol photons m}^{-2} \text{sec}^{-1}$ light intensity under short days (8-hour
352 light).

353

354 **GUS, eGFP Vector Construction**

355 Amplicons for pENTR™ Gateway construction were generated using Phusion
356 polymerase (New England Biolabs). Primers for amplifying the coding regions and
357 promoter regions from βCA1 (At3g01500) and βCA5 (At4g33580) were designed using
358 Integrated DNA Technologies primer design tools and were generated by Integrated DNA
359 Technologies (Table S1). PCR fragments were gel purified using the Qiaquick Gel
360 Extraction kit (Qiagen). 1 to 2 μL of purified PCR product was added to a pENTR™ master
361 mix (1 μL of a 1.2 M NaCl and 0.06 M MgCl_2 mix [Invitrogen], 1 μL pENTR™/dTOPO®
362 vector mix [Invitrogen], and dH_2O [Invitrogen] to final volume of 6 μL) for pENTR™ vector
363 construction. Vectors were transformed into *E. coli* TOP10 chemically competent cells
364 and plated onto YEP plates (for 1 L: 10 g peptone, 5 g NaCl, 10 g yeast extract, 15 g
365 agar) supplemented with $50 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ kanamycin. pENTR™ vectors were subjected to
366 restriction digestion and sequencing to confirm the correct orientation and sequence of
367 the construct. eGFP amplicons were recombined into the pDEST vector pB7FWG2
368 (Karimi et al., 2002) and GUS amplicons were recombined into the pDEST vector
369 pKGWFS7 (Karimi et al., 2002). The correct orientation of the pDEST™ vector was
370 confirmed via restriction digestion.

371 Constructs used for the complementation studies were assembled using the
372 GoldenGate modular cloning system (Weber et al., 2011; Patron et al., 2015). Linear

373 Level 0 gene fragments (promoters, coding regions, terminators) were synthesized by
374 Twist Biosciences (San Francisco, CA, United States) with defined Golden Gate
375 compatible overhangs and cloned via traditional digestion and ligation into Golden Gate
376 compatible acceptor plasmids. Next, Level 1 constructs were generated to express the
377 $\beta CA1$ or $\beta CA5$ genes under the control of the desired promoters. Finally, Level 1
378 constructs were assembled into Level 2 constructs to include a constitutively expressed
379 BASTA resistance cassette. Correct assembly of Level 2 backbones was confirmed via
380 restriction digestion.

381

382 ***A. tumefaciens* Transfection and Screening of Transformants**

383 Stable eGFP, GUS, and complementation lines were created following a modified
384 procedure (Weigel and Glazebrook, 2002). A total of 200 μL of transformed *A.*
385 *tumefaciens* was used to inoculate 200 mL of LB medium supplemented with antibiotics
386 ($30 \mu g mL^{-1}$ gentamycin and $10 \mu g mL^{-1}$ rifampicin for *A. tumefaciens* helper plasmids
387 and either $100 \mu g mL^{-1}$ spectinomycin for the eGFP and GUS vectors or $50 \mu g$
388 mL^{-1} kanamycin for the complementation vector). The cultures were grown overnight at
389 $28^{\circ}C$ with vigorous shaking, and cells were pelleted in the morning by centrifugation at
390 6,000 rpm using a Beckman J2-HS centrifuge and JA-10 rotor. Pelleted cells were
391 resuspended in 400 mL of *A. tumefaciens* infiltration medium (one-half-strength
392 Murashige and Skoog medium with Gamborg's vitamins from Caisson Laboratories, 5%
393 [w/v] Suc, $0.044 \mu M$ benzylaminopurine suspended in dimethyl sulfoxide, and $50 \mu L$
394 L^{-1} Silwet L-77 from Lehle Seeds). Stalks with flowers of Arabidopsis plants were dipped
395 in the *A. tumefaciens* infiltration medium for approximately 40 seconds and then laid
396 sideways in a flat with a covered dome to recover overnight, incubating in constant light
397 at $21^{\circ}C$ (Weigel and Glazebrook, 2002). Positive transformants were selected on soil by
398 spraying seedlings with a 1:1,000 dilution of BASTA (AgrEvo).

399

400 **RNA-seq analysis**

401 RNA-seq reads in roots and leaves for five selected genes. The genes included $\beta CA1$
402 (At3g01500) and $\beta CA5$ (At4g33580). For comparison of expression patterns, *PsbO*
403 (At3g50820) was chosen as a leaf-specific gene, $\gamma CA1$ (At1g19580) for its constitutive

404 expression and *PHT1* (At5g43350) served as an example of root-specific expression. In
405 all cases the same six libraries were used, each one a COL wildtype control study. Bars
406 represent averages of six RNA-seq libraries from <http://ipf.sustech.edu.cn/pub/athrna/>
407 (Zhang et al., 2020).

408

409 **Histochemical GUS Staining**

410 GUS staining was visualized following a modified protocol of Jefferson, Kavanagh, and
411 Bevan (1987). Plants and inflorescences were submerged in a GUS staining solution
412 (0.1M NaPO₄ pH 7, 10 mM EDTA, 0.1% Triton X-100, 1 mM K₃Fe(CN)₆, 2 mM 5-bromo,
413 4-chloro, 3-indol β -D-glucuronic acid [X-Gluc, from GoldBio] suspended in N, N-
414 dimethylformamide) and were placed in a 37°C incubator in the dark overnight. The
415 following morning, plants were taken out of the incubator and the GUS staining solution
416 was aspirated. Plant tissues were incubated in 100% (v/v) methanol at 60°C for 15 min
417 repeatedly until all chlorophyll was removed.

418

419 **Protoplast Preparation and eGFP Visualization**

420 Following the protocol of Wu et al. (2009), 2 g of leaf tissue was incubated in 10 mL of
421 enzyme solution (1% [w/v] cellulase from *Trichoderma viride* [Sigma], 0.25% [w/v]
422 pectinase from *Rhizopus* spp. [Sigma], 0.4 M mannitol, 10 mM CaCl₂, 20 mM KCl, 0.1%
423 [w/v] bovine serum albumin, and 20 mM MES at pH 5.7) for 1 h in light after placing Time
424 Tape on the upper epidermis of the leaves and removing the lower epidermis of the leaves
425 via Magic Tape. Protoplasts were then pelleted by centrifugation at 800 rpm for 3 min
426 using a Beckman J2-HS centrifuge and JS-13.1 rotor. Protoplasts were resuspended in
427 a solution containing 0.4 M mannitol, 15 mM MgCl₂, and 4 mM MES at pH 5.7. eGFP
428 fluorescence was visualized using protoplasts and leaves from stable eGFP plants with
429 a Leica SP2 confocal microscope. A 40X oil-emersion lens was used to visualize
430 protoplasts and a 20X objective lens was used to visualize intact cells from leaf samples.
431 eGFP and chlorophyll were excited using a krypton/argon laser tuned to 488 nm, and
432 eGFP and chlorophyll fluorescence were observed between the wavelengths of 500 to
433 520 nm and 660 to 700 nm, respectively.

434

435 **Genotyping T-DNA Lines Using Genomic PCR and Reverse Transcription-PCR**

436 DNA for genomic PCR was isolated from Arabidopsis leaves ground with a mortar and
437 pestle and incubated in Edward's extraction buffer (200 mM Tris-Cl, pH 7.5, 250
438 mM NaCl, 25 mM EDTA, and 0.5% [w/v] SDS). DNA was precipitated using 100% (v/v)
439 isopropanol followed by 70% (v/v) ethanol washes. Primers used can be found in Table
440 S1. RNA for reverse transcription was isolated from 80 mg of leaf tissue from 6-week-old
441 Arabidopsis plants grown in low CO₂ and short days using the Qiagen RNeasy Plant
442 minikit. Three micrograms of RNA were used for the reverse transcription reaction,
443 and cDNA was generated using the SuperScript First-Strand RT-PCR kit and protocol
444 (Invitrogen). cDNA at 0.5 µL was used for a 25-µL PCR using the standard protocol for
445 One Taq (New England Biolabs). Primers used can be found in Table S1.

446

447 **Rosette Area and Fresh Weight Measurements**

448 Images of plant lines were taken weekly, and rosette areas were measured by tracing the
449 outlines of the plants and obtaining the projected rosette area within each outline in
450 ImageJ (National Institutes of Health). Rosette areas were measured on three plants per
451 line. Fresh weights of above-ground plant mass were measured every week for each plant
452 line for 5 weeks. Three plants per line were used for fresh weight analysis.

453

454 **Immunoblots**

455 50 mg of leaf tissue was placed in a sterile 1.5 mL microcentrifuge tube and ground using
456 a sterile plastic pestle. 132 µL of Protein Extraction Buffer (1x TE, 1.2% SDS, 2.7%
457 sucrose, 7.5 µg mL⁻¹ bromophenol blue) was added to the ground leaf tissue. Samples
458 were vortexed and incubated on ice for 15 minutes before being centrifuged at 14,000
459 rpm for five minutes using a benchtop centrifuge. The supernatant was collected and
460 placed in a new sterile 0.5 mL microcentrifuge tube whereas the pellet was discarded.
461 Protein concentrations were quantified using the Bradford protein assay kit (Pierce). 2-
462 mercaptoethanol was added to a final concentration of 350 mM and then samples were
463 incubated at 100°C for three minutes. 20 µg of total protein was added to a 12%
464 polyacrylamide gel and proteins were electrophoresed (Bio-Rad) before being transferred
465 to a PVDF membrane (Bio-Rad) using the Semi-Dry system. The membrane was blocked

466 in 1% bovine serum albumin and TTBS (TBS containing 0.1% Tween) for 1 hr at 4°C and
467 they were treated with primary antibody directed against *Arabidopsis* β CA1 (Proteintech
468 Group) at a final dilution of 1:20,000 and β CA5 antibody (Agrisera) at a final dilution of 1:
469 10,000. These membranes were allowed to incubate overnight at 4°C. The following
470 morning, the membrane was washed five times with TTBS before being placed in a TBSB
471 solution containing a Bio-Rad goat anti-rabbit secondary antibody at a final dilution of
472 1:20,000. The membrane was allowed to incubate at room temperature for one hour and
473 was then washed five times with TTBS. A BioRad chemiluminescence instrument was
474 used to observe the protein bands.

475

476 **Seeds growing on malonate**

477 To test the effect of malonate on *Arabidopsis* plant growth, sterilized wild type and β CA5
478 seeds were placed on MS agar plates, MS + sodium malonate (2 mM), MS + sodium
479 malonate (2 mM) + Tween-60 and Tween-80 (final concentration of 300uM). Tween-60
480 and Tween-80 were used in this experiment as a detergent that increases the malonate
481 uptake. Growth of these seedlings was examined after 14 d of germination.

482

483 **Pollen tube germination**

484 Three inflorescences from each plant type (wild-type and β ca5) were cut and left to air
485 dry for 10 minutes. In a sterile hood, two square plates were prepared with a Kimwipe
486 and 700 microliters of sterilized water to emulate a humid environment suitable for pollen
487 germination. MS media was prepared with 10 g/100 mL sucrose, 0.01 g/100 mL boric
488 acid, 0.011 g/100 mL calcium nitrate, 0.43 g/100 mL MS salts + nutrients, and 1 g/100
489 mL agarose and adjusted to a pH of 6.0. Each plate contained a three-well plate in which
490 600 μ L of MS media was added. The first well was used as the negative control, the
491 second well contained pollen grains extracted from wild-type plants, and the final well
492 contained pollen grains extracted from β ca5 plants. Pollen grains were extracted by
493 dipping the inflorescences of the plant into the media of the well. Plates were incubated
494 under ambient (400 μ L L⁻¹ CO₂) and 3% (30,000 μ L L⁻¹) CO₂.

495

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498 confocal microscopy. This work was supported by the Realizing Improved Photosynthetic
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500 made possible through support from the Bill & Melinda Gates Foundation, FFAR and
501 FCDO, grant OPP1172157.

502

503 **Figure legends**

504 **Figure 1.** Both β CA1 and β CA5 are chloroplast proteins. Protoplasts from stably-
505 expressing β CA1-eGFP and β CA5-eGFP Arabidopsis lines were imaged using confocal
506 microscopy. Yellow represents eGFP fluorescence and blue represents chlorophyll
507 autofluorescence.

508 **Figure 2.** Arabidopsis lines missing either β CA1, β CA5 or both CAs were constructed.
509 A); Locations of the T-DNA insertions within the β CA1 and β CA5 genes. The β CA1 T-
510 DNA insertion (SALK_106570) is in the ninth exon of the β CA1 gene. The β CA5 T-DNA
511 insertion (SALK_121932) is in the eighth exon of the β CA5 gene. Triangles represent T-
512 DNA insertions and black arrows represent locations of gene specific (F and R) primers
513 and insert (I) primers. Blue boxes and grey lines represent exons and introns,
514 respectively. Red boxes and red arrows represent the 5' and 3' UTRs, respectively. cTP
515 = chloroplast transit peptide. B); Western blots were performed using antibodies against
516 β CA1 and β CA5. These two proteins are missing in their respective mutant lines. An SDS-
517 Page gel loaded with the same protein samples and stained with Coomassie blue is
518 shown to the right of each blot.

519 **Figure 3.** Plants disrupted in β CA5 showed severely reduced growth at ambient CO₂. A);
520 Wild-type (COL), β ca1, β ca5, and β ca1 β ca5 plants grown under ambient CO₂ (400 μ L L⁻¹
521 ¹) or high CO₂ (30,000 μ L L⁻¹) on an 8-hour light/16-hour dark photoperiod. B); Average
522 plant rosette area at different weeks post-germination when grown in ambient or high CO₂
523 and on an 8-hour light/16-hour dark photoperiod. C); Average plant fresh weight at
524 different weeks post-germination when grown in ambient or high CO₂ and on an 8-hour
525 light/16-hour dark photoperiod. Error bars represent plus and minus one standard
526 deviation for the means of four plants. There were no significant differences among the
527 plants grown at high CO₂, but the growth of β ca5 and β ca1 β ca5 plants was significantly
528 reduced compared to wild-type (COL) and β ca1 plants when grown on ambient CO₂.

529 **Figure 4.** β CA1 and β CA5 expression patterns. A); RNA-seq reads in roots and leaves
530 for five selected genes. β CA1 is undetectable in root tissue. β CA1 (At3g01500) shows
531 leaf-specific expression like *PsbO* (At3g50820). In contrast, β CA5 (At4g33580) is
532 expressed in all tissues examined, similar to γ CA1 (At1g19580) expression. *PHT1*

533 (At5g43350) serves as an example of root-specific expression. Bars represent averages
534 of six RNA-seq libraries from <http://ipf.sustech.edu.cn/pub/athrna/> (Zhang et al., 2020).
535 FPKM = fragments per kilobase of transcript per million fragments mapped. B); Vegetative
536 tissues of three-week-old Arabidopsis plants stably transformed with either *pβCA1::GUS*
537 or *pβCA5::GUS*. C); Root tissues of three-week-old Arabidopsis plants stably
538 transformed with either *pβCA1::GUS* or *pβCA5::GUS*. The *pβCA1::GUS* plants show
539 GUS expression only in the rosette leaves, whereas *pβCA5::GUS* plants show GUS
540 expression in root and shoot meristematic regions and younger leaves.

541 **Figure 5.** Expressing the *βCA1* and *βCA5* coding regions in *βca5* plants restored wild-
542 type growth in ambient CO₂. All plants were grown on an 8-hour light/16- hour dark
543 photoperiod with a light intensity of 120 μmol photons m⁻² sec⁻¹. The plants labeled
544 “*ubi::βCA1*” and “*ubi::βCA5*” are *βca5* KO plants transformed with the indicated genes.

545 **Figure 6.** Malonate stimulates growth in *βca5* plants. A); Growth of *βca5* plants was
546 observed on MS media and MS + Tween 80/60 + 2mM malonate. *βca5* plants showed
547 growth improvements on MS + Tween 80/60 + 2 mM malonate in comparison to the MS
548 media. B); Wild-type (COL) plants exhibited normal growth on MS media. Growth of wild-
549 type roots increased on MS + Tween 80/60 + 2 mM malonate. The width and height of
550 each grid square is 1 cm. All plants were grown in ambient CO₂ for ten days.

551 **Figure 7.** Expression of *βCA1* and *βCA5* in flowers. *βCA1* is not expressed in pollen but
552 *βCA5* is expressed in pollen. Arrows point to pollen grains. The plants shown are
553 expressing GUS driven by either the *βCA1* or *βCA5* promoter as described in the legend
554 of figure 2.

555 **Figure 8.** Pollen tube germination in *βca5* plants increased under high CO₂. A); Pollen
556 germination of *βca5* mutants was observed in ambient and high CO₂ overnight
557 incubations. In ambient air, *βca5* mutants showed no pollen germination. However, in
558 high CO₂, germination occurred with significant germination percentage and germ tube
559 lengthening. B); Ambient CO₂ germination of the wild-type plant was significantly lower
560 than the high CO₂ germination percentages; the same trend is seen in germ tube length.
561 Bars shown for germ tube length represent averages of 30 germination tube lengths.

562 **Figure 9.** *βca5* complementation model. Inside the root plastids of a wild-type Arabidopsis
563 plant, β CA5 catalyzes the conversion of CO_2 to HCO_3^- , which is used in lipid biosynthesis.
564 When β CA5 is knocked out, the plant's growth is stunted on ambient CO_2 since β CA5 is
565 not present in the root plastids to catalyze the conversion of CO_2 to HCO_3^- . If β CA5 or
566 β CA1 (driven by a constitutive promoter) are put back into the *βca5* plant, normal growth
567 is restored. β CA5 or β CA1 is present in the root plastids to catalyze the conversion of
568 CO_2 to HCO_3^- , which restores the plant's lipid biosynthesis capabilities.

569 **Supplemental Data**

570 **Table S1.** List of primers used in this study.

571 **Supplementary Figure 1.** Additional images of β CA1 and β CA5 localization in
572 protoplasts. Yellow represents eGFP fluorescence and blue represents chlorophyll
573 autofluorescence.

574 **Supplementary Figure 2.** Arabidopsis lines missing β CA1, lines missing β CA5 and lines
575 missing both β CA1 and β CA5 were constructed. A); The β CA1 and β CA5 genes were
576 disrupted by T DNA insertions. Genomic PCR on wild-type, β CA1, β CA5 and β CA1 β CA5
577 plants show that the T-DNA insert SALK_106570 is present in the
578 β CA1 gene and the SALK_121932 is present in the β CA5 gene. Both inserts disrupt their
579 corresponding genes. B); The *βca1* and *βca5* mutant lines show reduced transcription of
580 the β CA1 and β CA5 genes respectively. RT-PCR using gene specific primers show that
581 β CA1 message cannot be detected in the *βca1* and *βca1βca5* mutants and β CA5
582 messages cannot be detected in the *βca5* and *βca1βca5* mutants. 3 μ g of RNA was used
583 from each sample to carry out RT-PCR.

584 **Supplementary Figure 3.** Western blots showing β CA1 and β CA5 expression in roots
585 and shoots. A); Western blot showing β CA1 (25.7 kDa) was only detected in shoots.
586 Lanes 1 and 2 were loaded with protein extracted from shoot samples. Lanes 3 and 4
587 were loaded with protein extracted from root samples. An SDS-Page gel loaded with the
588 same protein samples and stained with Coomassie blue is shown to the right. B); Western
589 blot showing β CA5 (26.8 kDa) was detected in shoots and roots. Lanes 1 and 2 were
590 loaded with protein extracted from shoot samples. Lanes 3 and 4 were loaded with protein

591 extracted from root samples. An SDS-Page gel loaded with the same protein samples
592 and stained with Coomassie blue is shown to the right.

593 **Supplementary Figure 4.** $\beta CA5$ is missing in $\beta ca5$ plants, while $\beta CA1$ and $\beta CA5$ are
594 present in their respective complimented lines. Genomic DNA was extracted from $\beta ca5$
595 plants, plants complimented with an $ubi::\beta CA1$ construct, and plants complimented with
596 an $ubi::\beta CA5$ construct. A); $\beta CA5$ is missing in lines 1, 2, 3, and 4 of $\beta ca5$ plants but is
597 present in wild-type lines 1 and 2. B); The $ubi::\beta CA1$ construct is present in lines 1, 2, 3,
598 and 4 of $\beta CA1$ -complimented plants. Native $\beta CA1$ is present in wild-type lines 1 and 2.
599 C); The $ubi::\beta CA5$ construct is present in lines 1, 2, and 3 of $\beta CA5$ -complimented plants.
600 Native $\beta CA5$ is present in the wild-type. D); Gene maps of $\beta CA5$ and $\beta CA1$ show the
601 sizes of the genomic DNA fragments and the CDS fragments amplified by the primers
602 used to perform the above PCRs.

603

604 **References**

- 605 Aguilera J, Van Dijken JP, De Winder JH, Pronk JT (2005) Carbonic anhydrase
606 (Nce103p): an essential biosynthetic enzyme for growth of *Saccharomyces*
607 *cerevisiae* at atmospheric carbon dioxide pressure. *Biochem J* 391: 311-316
- 608 Baud S, Bellec Y, Miquel M, Bellini C, Caboche M, Lepiniec L, Faure JD, Rochat C
609 (2004) Gurke and pasticchino3 mutants affected in embryo development are
610 impaired in acetyl-CoA carboxylase. *EMBO Rep* 5: 515-520
- 611 DiMario RJ, Quebedeaux JC, Longstreth DJ, Dassanayake M, Hartman MM, Moroney
612 JV (2016) The cytoplasmic carbonic anhydrases β ca2 and β ca4 are required for
613 optimal plant growth at low CO₂. *Plant Physiol* 171: 280-293
- 614 DiMario RJ, Clayton H, Mukherjee A, Ludwig M, Moroney JV (2017) Plant Carbonic
615 Anhydrases: Structures, Locations, Evolution, and Physiological Roles. *Mol Plant*
616 10: 30-46
- 617 Epstein E, Bloom AJ (2005) Mineral Nutrition of Plants: Principles and Perspectives, Ed
618 2. Sinauer Associates, Sunderland. pp 31
- 619 Fabre N, Reiter IM, Becuwe-Linka N, Genty B, Rumeau D (2007) Characterization and
620 expression analysis of genes encoding alpha and beta carbonic anhydrases in
621 *Arabidopsis*. *Plant Cell Environ* 30: 617-629
- 622 Ferreira FJ, Guo C, Coleman JR (2008) Reduction of plastid-localized carbonic
623 anhydrase activity results in reduced *Arabidopsis* seedling survivorship. *Plant*
624 *Physiol* 147: 585-594
- 625 Götz R, Gnann A, Zimmermann FK (1999) Deletion of the carbonic anhydrase-like gene
626 NCE103 of the yeast *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* causes an oxygen-sensitive
627 growth defect. *Yeast* 15: 855-864
- 628 Herbert D, Price LJ, Alban C, Dehaye L, Job D, Cole DJ, Pallett KE, Harwood JL (1996)
629 Kinetic studies on two isoforms of acetyl-CoA carboxylase from maize leaves.
630 *Biochem J* 318: 997-1006
- 631 Hewett-Emmett D, Tashian RE (1996) Functional diversity, conservation, and
632 convergence in the evolution of the alpha-, beta-, and gamma-carbonic
633 anhydrase gene families. *Mol Phylogenet Evol* 5: 50-77
- 634 Hines KM, Chaudhari V, Edgeworth KN, Owens TG, Hanson MR (2021) Absence of
635 carbonic anhydrase in chloroplasts affects C(3) plant development but not
636 photosynthesis. *Proc Natl Acad Sci U S A* 118
- 637 Hoang CV, Chapman KD (2002) Regulation of carbonic anhydrase gene expression in
638 cotyledons of cotton (*Gossypium hirsutum* L.) seedlings during post-germinative
639 growth. *Plant Mol Biol* 49: 449-458
- 640 Hu H, Boisson-Dernier A, Israelsson-Nordström M, Böhmer M, Xue S, Ries A, Godoski
641 J, Kuhn JM, Schroeder JI (2010) Carbonic anhydrases are upstream regulators
642 of CO₂-controlled stomatal movements in guard cells. *Nat Cell Biol* 12: 87-93;
643 sup pp 81-18
- 644 Iverson TM, Alber BE, Kisker C, Ferry JG, Rees DC (2000) A closer look at the active
645 site of gamma-class carbonic anhydrases: high-resolution crystallographic
646 studies of the carbonic anhydrase from *Methanosarcina thermophila*.
647 *Biochemistry* 39: 9222-9231

648 Jefferson RA, Kavanagh TA, Bevan MW (1987) GUS fusions: beta-glucuronidase as a
649 sensitive and versatile gene fusion marker in higher plants. *EMBO J* 6: 3901-
650 3907

651 Jensen EL, Maberly SC, Gonterro B (2020) Insights on the Functions and
652 Ecophysiological Relevance of the Diverse Carbonic Anhydrases in Microalgae.
653 *Int J Mol Sci* 21

654 Karimi M, Inzé D, Depicker A (2002) GATEWAY™ vectors for Agrobacterium-mediated
655 plant transformation. *Trends Plant Sci* 7: 193-195

656 Kimber MS, Pai EF (2000) The active site architecture of *Pisum sativum* beta-carbonic
657 anhydrase is a mirror image of that of alpha-carbonic anhydrases. *Embo j* 19:
658 1407-1418

659 Kisker C, Schindelin H, Alber BE, Ferry JG, Rees DC (1996) A left-hand beta-helix
660 revealed by the crystal structure of a carbonic anhydrase from the archaeon
661 *Methanosarcina thermophila*. *Embo j* 15: 2323-2330

662 Liljas A, Kannan KK, Bergstén PC, Waara I, Fridborg K, Strandberg B, Carlbom U,
663 Järup L, Lövgren S, Petef M (1972) Crystal Structure of Human Carbonic
664 Anhydrase C. *Nature New Biology* 235: 131-137

665 Lynch CJ, Fox H, Hazen SA, Stanley BA, Dodgson S, Lanoue KF (1995) Role of
666 hepatic carbonic anhydrase in de novo lipogenesis. *Biochem J* 310 (Pt 1): 197-
667 202

668 Majeau N, Arnoldo MA, Coleman JR (1994) Modification of carbonic anhydrase activity
669 by antisense and over-expression constructs in transgenic tobacco. *Plant Mol*
670 *Biol* 25: 377-385

671 Medina-Puche L, Castelló MJ, Canet JV, Lamilla J, Colombo ML, Tornero P (2017) β -
672 carbonic anhydrases play a role in salicylic acid perception in *Arabidopsis*. *PLoS*
673 *One* 12

674 Ohlrogge J, Browse J (1995) Lipid biosynthesis. *The Plant Cell* 7: 957-970

675 Patron NJ, Orzaez D, Marillonnet S, Warzecha H, Matthewman C, et al. 2015.
676 Standards for plant synthetic biology: a common syntax for exchange of DNA
677 parts. *New Phytol* 208:13-9

678 Price GD, Caemmerer SV, Evans JR, Yu JW, Lloyd JM, Oja V, Kell P, Harrison K,
679 Gallagher A, Badger MR (2004) Specific reduction of chloroplast carbonic
680 anhydrase activity by antisense RNA in transgenic tobacco plants has a minor
681 effect on photosynthetic CO₂ assimilation. *Planta* 193: 331-340

682 Sasaki Y, Nagano Y (2004) Plant acetyl-CoA carboxylase: structure, biosynthesis,
683 regulation, and gene manipulation for plant breeding. *Bioscience, Biotechnology,*
684 *and Biochemistry* 68: 1175-1184

685 Sun Q, Zybailov B, Majeran W, Friso G, Olinares PDB, van Wijk KJ (2009) PPDB, the
686 plant proteomics database at Cornell. *Nucl Acids Res* 37

687 Tobin AJ (1970) Carbonic anhydrase from parsley leaves. *J Biol Chem* 245: 2656-2666

688 Weber E, Engler C, Gruetzner R, Werner S, Marillonnet S (2011) A modular cloning
689 system for standardized assembly of multigene constructs. *PLoS One* 6

690 Weigel D, Glazebrook J (2002) How to transform *Arabidopsis*. *Arabidopsis A Laboratory*
691 *Manual*, Cold Spring Harbor Laboratory Press, Cold Spring Harbor, pp 119-141

692 Wu Y, Suhasini AN, Brosh Jr RM (2009) Welcome the family of FANCD1-like helicases to
693 the block of genome stability maintenance proteins. *Cell Mol Life Sci* 66: 1209–
694 1222
695 Zhang H, Zhang F, Yu Y, Feng L, Jia J, Liu B, Li B, Guo H, Zhai J (2020) A
696 comprehensive online database for exploring ~20,000 public Arabidopsis RNA-
697 seq libraries. *Molecular Plant* 13: 1231–1233

Figure 1. Both β CA1 and β CA5 are chloroplast proteins. Protoplasts from stably-expressing β CA1-eGFP and β CA5-eGFP Arabidopsis lines were imaged using confocal microscopy. Yellow represents eGFP fluorescence and blue represents chlorophyll autofluorescence.

2. Arabidopsis lines missing either β CA1, β CA5 or both CAs were constructed by T-DNA insertions within the β CA1 and β CA5 genes. The β CA1 T-DNA insertion (SALK_106570) is in the ninth exon of the β CA1 gene. The β CA5 T-DNA insertion (SALK_121932) is in the eighth exon of the β CA5 gene. Triangles represent T-DNA insertion sites. Arrows represent locations of gene specific (F and R) primers and insert (I) primers. Red and grey lines represent exons and introns, respectively. Red boxes and red arrows represent the 5' and 3' UTRs, respectively. cTP = chloroplast transit peptide. B); Western blot analysis of β CA1 and β CA5 protein levels. These two proteins are missing in the respective mutant lines. An SDS-Page gel loaded with the same protein samples and stained with Coomassie blue is shown to the right of each blot.

A

Figure 3. Plants disrupted in $\beta CA5$ showed severely reduced growth at ambient CO₂. A); Wild-type (COL), $\beta ca1$, $\beta ca5$, and $\beta ca1\beta ca5$ plants grown under ambient CO₂ (400 $\mu\text{L L}^{-1}$) or high CO₂ (30,000 $\mu\text{L L}^{-1}$) on an 8-hour light/16-hour dark photoperiod. B); Average plant rosette area at different weeks post-germination when grown in ambient or high CO₂ and on an 8-hour light/16-hour dark photoperiod. C); Average plant fresh weight at different weeks post-germination when grown in ambient or high CO₂ and on an 8-hour light/16-hour dark photoperiod. Error bars represent plus and minus one standard deviation for the means of four plants. There were no significant differences among the plants grown at high CO₂, but the growth of $\beta ca5$ and $\beta ca1\beta ca5$ plants was significantly reduced compared to wild-type (COL) and $\beta ca1$ plants when grown on ambient CO₂.

A

Figure 4. $\beta CA1$ and $\beta CA5$ expression patterns. A); RNA-seq reads in roots and leaves for five selected genes. $\beta CA1$ is undetectable in root tissue. $\beta CA1$ (At3g01500) shows leaf-specific expression like *PsbO* (At3g50820). In contrast, $\beta CA5$ (At4g33580) is expressed in all tissues examined, similar to $\gamma CA1$ (At1g19580) expression. *PHT1* (At5g43350) serves as an example of root-specific expression. Bars represent averages of six RNA-seq libraries from <http://ipf.sustech.edu.cn/pub/athrna/> (Zhang et al., 2020). FPKM = fragments per kilobase of transcript per million fragments mapped. B); Vegetative tissues of three-week-old Arabidopsis plants stably transformed with either $p\beta CA1::GUS$ or $p\beta CA5::GUS$. C); Root tissues of three-week-old Arabidopsis plants stably transformed with either $p\beta CA1::GUS$ or $p\beta CA5::GUS$. The $p\beta CA1::GUS$ plants show GUS expression only in the rosette leaves, whereas $p\beta CA5::GUS$ plants show GUS expression in root and shoot meristematic regions and younger leaves.

$\beta ca5$

$\beta ca5$ + Tween 80/60 +
2mM malonate

COL

COL + Tween 80/60 +
2mM malonate

6. Malonate stimulates growth in $\beta ca5$ plants. A); Growth of $\beta ca5$ plants on MS media and MS + Tween 80/60 + 2mM malonate. $\beta ca5$ plants showed improvements on MS + Tween 80/60 + 2 mM malonate in comparison to B); Wild-type (COL) plants exhibited normal growth on MS media. Growth of wild-type plants increased on MS + Tween 80/60 + 2 mM malonate. The width and height of each plant is 1 cm. All plants were grown in ambient CO₂ for ten days.

Figure 5. Expressing the $\beta CA1$ and $\beta CA5$ coding regions in $\beta ca5$ plants restored wild-type growth in ambient CO_2 . All plants were grown on an 8-hour light/16-hour dark photoperiod with a light intensity of $120 \mu\text{mol photons m}^{-2} \text{sec}^{-1}$. The plants labeled “ubi:: $\beta CA1$ ” and “ubi:: $\beta CA5$ ” are $\beta ca5$ KO plants transformed with the indicated genes.

Figure 7. Expression of $\beta CA1$ and $\beta CA5$ in flowers. $\beta CA1$ is not expressed in pollen but $\beta CA5$ is expressed in pollen. Arrows point to pollen grains. The plants shown are expressing GUS driven by either the $\beta CA1$ or $\beta CA5$ promoter as described in the legend of figure 2.

Ambient

High CO₂

B

WT

Ambient

High CO₂

Figure 8. Pollen tube germination in $\beta ca5$ plants increased under high CO₂. A); Pollen germination of $\beta ca5$ mutants was observed in ambient and high CO₂ overnight incubations. In ambient air, $\beta ca5$ mutants showed no pollen germination. However, in high CO₂, germination occurred with significant germination percentage and germ tube lengthening. B); Ambient CO₂ germination of the wild type plant was significantly lower than the high

Figure 9 . *beta-ca5* complementation model. Inside the root plastids of a wild-type Arabidopsis plant, βCA5 catalyzes the conversion of CO_2 to HCO_3^- , which is used in lipid biosynthesis. When βCA5 is knocked out, the plant's growth is stunted on ambient CO_2 since βCA5 is not present in the root plastids to catalyze the conversion of CO_2 to HCO_3^- . If βCA5 or βCA1 (driven by a constitutive promoter) are put back into the *beta-ca5* plant, normal growth is restored.

Supplementary Figure 1. Additional images of β CA1 and β CA5 localization in protoplasts. Yellow represents eGFP fluorescence and blue represents chlorophyll autofluorescence.

Supplementary Figure 2. Arabidopsis lines missing β CA1, lines missing β CA5 and lines missing both β CA1 and β CA5 were constructed. A); The β CA1 and β CA5 genes were disrupted by T-DNA insertions. Genomic PCR of wild-type, β ca1, β ca5 and β ca1 β ca5 plants show that the T-DNA insert SALK_106570 is present in the β CA1 gene and the T-DNA insert SALK-121932 is present in the β CA5 gene. Both inserts disrupt their corresponding genes. B); The β ca1 and β ca5 mutant lines show reduced transcription of the β CA1 and β CA5 genes, respectively. RT-PCR using gene-specific primers show that β CA1 messages cannot be detected in the β ca1 and β ca1 β ca5 mutants and β CA5 messages cannot be detected in the β ca5 and β ca1 β ca5 mutants. 3 μ g of RNA was used from each sample to carry out RT-PCR.

Supplementary Figure 3. Western blots showing β CA1 and β CA5 expression in roots and shoots. A); Western blot showing β CA1 (25.7 kDa) was only detected in shoots. Lanes 1 and 2 were loaded with protein extracted from shoot samples. Lanes 3 and 4 were loaded with protein extracted from root samples. An SDS-Page gel loaded with the same protein samples and stained with Coomassie blue is shown to the right. B); Western blot showing β CA5 (26.8 kDa) was detected in shoots and roots. Lanes 1 and 2 were loaded with protein extracted from shoot samples. Lanes 3 and 4 were loaded with protein extracted from root samples. An SDS-Page gel loaded with the same protein samples and stained with Coomassie blue is shown to the right.

Supplementary Figure 4. *βCA5* is missing in *βca5* plants, while *βCA1* and *βCA5* are present in their respective complemented lines. Genomic DNA was extracted from *βca5* plants, plants complemented with an *ubi::βCA1* construct, and plants complemented with an *ubi::βCA5* construct. A); *βCA5* is missing in lines 1, 2, 3, and 4 of *βca5* plants but is present in wild-type lines 1 and 2. B); The *ubi::βCA1* construct is present in lines 1, 2, 3, and 4 of *βCA1*-complemented plants. Native *βCA1* is present in wild-type lines 1 and 2. C); The *ubi::βCA5* construct is present in lines 1, 2, and 3 of *βCA5*-complemented plants. Native *βCA5* is present in the wild-type. D); Gene maps of *βCA5* and *βCA1* show the sizes of the genomic DNA fragments and the CDS fragments amplified by the primers used to perform the above PCRs.